

CONCENTRATED LANGUAGE ENCOUNTER (CLE) METHOD AND READING VISUAL PERCEPTUAL SKILL AMONG PRIMARY ONE PUPILS

By

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Abstract

The study investigates the effect of concentrated language visual method on developing reading visual perceptual skills among primary one pupils in Obudu Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study specifically focuses on the effect of the Concentrated Language Encounter (CLE) method in visual discrimination and visual memory skills, while adopting the quasi-experimental research design in which experimental group and control groups were used. The cluster sampling technique was adopted, and a sample of 50 pupils was drawn from the primary school under study. The instrument used for data collection was a pupil-centered questionnaire. The instrument was scrutinized, validated, and its reliability was determined using the Cronbach alpha reliability method. Data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), tested at the .05 level of significance. Findings reveal a significant effect of the CLE method on Visual Discrimination Skill and Visual Memory Skill. Based on the findings, recommendations were made concerning the effective incorporation of CLE method in public primary schools.

Keywords: Concentrated Language Encounter (CLE), Reading Visual Perceptual Skills, Visual Discrimination Skills, and Visual Memory Skills.

Introduction

Reading is a critical tool for pupils functioning not just for learning, but also the basis of all aspects of learning and successful living in today's complex society (Ikwen, 2015). Learning to read demands an effective beginning reading instruction, which is key to creating strong, competent readers and preventing reading difficulties. The skill acquired in reading helps in promoting the acquisition of language skills like listening, speaking, and writing. Enabling children to improve their self-confidence since they are given opportunities to interact with their peers and adults too. It enhances independence and helps curb the tendency of children who are highly aggressive during group activities. This necessitates teachers' acquaintance with foundational reading skills for beginning readers and teaching strategies to enforce the development of the beginning reading skills.

Visual perceptual skills, which refer to the brain's ability to make sense of what the eye(s) see(s), are necessary for school success, such as reading, writing, and maths, as well as life skills.

Visual perception skills can be broken into the following sub-skills:

Visual discrimination is the ability to find similarities and differences between objects or written symbols.

Visual memory and visual sequential memory involve the ability to remember things seen visually and to recall a sequence of objects in the correct order.

Thus, the literature evidence has shown that the use of Concentrated Language Encounter (CLE) is effective in developing beginning reading skills. However, studies conducted using the CLE method to develop visual perception are rare, and incremental reports and worries about the rate at which pupils pass out of primary schools with poor reading skills. It is based on this backdrop that the researcher embarked on this study in order to ascertain whether concentrated language-encounter could develop beginning reading visual perceptual skills.

Statement of the problem

Nigerian public primary school pupils experience poor reading ability and poor academic performance.

This paper, therefore, investigates the effect of the Concentrated Language Encounter (CLE) method in developing beginning reading visual perceptual skills among primary one pupils.

Research questions

Two research questions were raised to guide this study are:

1. What is the effect of the concentrated language encounter method in developing visual discrimination skills among primary one pupils?
2. What is the effect of the concentrated language encounter method in developing visual memory skills among primary one pupils?

Two null hypotheses tested at the .05 level of significance, which were formulated to guide this study, are:

Ho₁: There is no significant effect of the concentrated language encounter method in developing visual discrimination skills among primary one pupils.

Ho₂: There is no significant effect of the concentrated language encounter method in developing visual memory skills among primary one pupils.

Research design

This quasi-experimental design was adopted for this study. Quasi-experimental research involves experimental studies used to estimate the causal impact of an intervention on the target population. It was preferred primarily because intact groups were desired in order to avoid disrupting the school system. The population of this study consisted of primary one pupils, beginning readers in Obudu Local Government Area, while the sample comprised 50 pupils purposively selected. A questionnaire was designed, validated, and used as an instrument for data collection.

Method of data analysis

Data were analyzed using the hypothesis-by-hypothesis method of data analysis. Each hypothesis was tested at the .05 level of significance.

Results

The results of the findings are thus presented at a .05 significance level.

Research question 1: What is the effect of the concentrated language encounter method in developing visual discrimination skills?

TABLE 1: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) result on the effect of concentrated language encounter method on acquisition of visual discrimination skills

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev
Control Group	25	9.5200	1.55778
Experimental group 2	25	15.6800	3.14537
Total	50	12.6000	3.96412

Source	Type II Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	496.683 ^a	2	248.342	42.705	.000
Intercept	114.034	1	114.034	19.610	.000
Pretest	22.363	1	22.363	3.846	.056
Treatment	496.078	1	496.078	85.306	.000
Error	273.317	47	5.815		
Total	8708.000	50			
Corrected Total	770.000	49			

a. R Squared = .645 (Adjusted R Squared = .630)

TABLE 2: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) result on the effect of the concentrated language encounter method in developing visual memory skills

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev
		10.4000	1.11803
Control group	25		
Experimental group 4	25	17.5800	1.86458
Total	50	14.0400	3.97933

Source	Type II Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	663.150 ^a	2	331.575	138.193	.000
Intercept	327.596	1	327.596	136.534	.000
Pretest	.670	1	.670	.279	.600
Group 4	634.145	1	634.145	262.297	.000
Error	112.770	47	2.399		
Total	10632.000	50			
Corrected Total	775.920	49			

a. R Squared = .855 (Adjusted R Squared = .848)

Discussion of findings

The findings of the study showed that the use of the concentrated language encounter method in teaching beginning reading visual perceptual skills has a significant effect on the academic achievements of the pupils. The results are in line with the pilot study of Andzayi & Ikwen (2014), which determined the effect of the Concentrated Language Encounter (CLE) method in developing primary one pupils' reading level, oracy skills level, English sight words level, print awareness skills level, phono-phonemic awareness skills level, letter recognition skills, and comprehension skills.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, public primary school pupils should be taught using the Concentrated Language Encounter (CLE) method. Since the CLE developed visual perceptual skills of pupils, teachers should include the CLE in their lesson plan.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The failure of students' reading skills also affects their success in other courses negatively. Therefore, teachers should prepare activities aiming at students' reading development in the yearly school years.
2. When their children are in the pre-school period, parents should buy visual materials such as books, magazines, and newspapers that contain plenty of images, read them to their children, and ask their children to examine these materials. Beginning from the first grade, children can develop their visual perception and reading skills by reading and examination of written materials with their parents.
3. Nigerian primary school pupils in the rural areas are more disadvantaged in terms of preparatory instruction before the commencement of Primary One, either due to the economic status of the parents or to the prevalent poverty level of rural communities. Acquisition of beginning reading skills should be adequately supported by Government policies through the Federal and State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) with the aggressive provision of requisite physical infrastructures in Nigerian primary schools. Such improvements in infrastructure, especially in the rural areas, would enhance the attainment of some of the Millennium Development Goals in Nigeria.
4. The standard of literacy in Nigeria is a major problem, as many pupils cannot read simple books by the time they are admitted into Class One. The automatic admission of pupils into Primary One and automatic promotion of pupils into the next class, even when they fail, has worsened the standard of education in the country. The basic pre-reading skills that should have been developed before commencement of Primary Class One are often absent. Most pupils in rural communities are not often exposed to any formal education before being admitted into Class One. The introduction of Concentrated Language Encounter would be vital in preventing further deterioration in the standard of education.
5. The findings from the study have implications for contribution to knowledge in terms of short-time in-service training workshop and constant capacity-building workshops to train and retrain all Primary school teachers and their Head Teachers on how to use the Concentrated Language Encounter method to develop visual form constancy, visual discrimination, visual figure-ground, and visual memory skills in their pupils. Training and re-training in these skills would obviously help to boost the provision of quality education to Nigerian citizens in the 21st century.

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